

Jewish Theology as a Science in the Context of Post-Shoah Germany

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Abstract: This paper analyses the contested institutionalization of Jewish theology in contemporary Germany, focusing on the founding and crisis of the School of Jewish Theology at the University of Potsdam. It situates this development within broader debates over the scientific status of theology and the conditions under which it gains institutional legitimacy in secular, democratic societies. Following Paul Feyerabend’s theology-sensitive call to contextualize science in its historical and sociological dimensions, the paper challenges essentialist accounts of both science and religion. It argues that the emergence of academic Jewish theology in Germany must be understood as part of a shifting landscape of Germany’s social system of public knowledge, shaped by various factors, including political culture, communal authority, and contested epistemic norms. In doing so, the paper aims to contribute to current debates about pluralism, religious authority, and the role of theology in the modern university.

Keywords: Feyerabend, Jewish theology, science and religion, Germany, Wissenschaft des Judentums, university politics, epistemic pluralism, institutional legitimacy, theology as public knowledge, secularization.

“Like the defenders of the One True Religion before them [scientists] insinuate that their standards are essential for arriving at the Truth.” (Feyerabend 1975, 164)

“Our goal is to save Jewish theology in Germany.”
(The president of the University of Potsdam in the fall of 2022; *Jüdische Allgemeine*, 2022)

According to Menachem Fisch (2017), pluralism is constitutive of Judaism. In this paper, I examine how Judaism’s inherent pluralism fares within an increasingly pluralist society. Confessional theology at public universities in Germany is currently undergoing a profound transformation—from a predominantly monolithic (Christian) framework to a more pluralist one that includes Islamic and Jewish theology. I argue that this transformation is bound to affect the understanding of theology as an academic discipline with bearing on the larger question whether theology is a science.

Here is the roadmap for what follows. After introducing the paper’s aims and methods (1), I discuss Germany’s distinctive model of theological faculties (2), followed by an account of the Central Council of Jews in Germany and its structural role within Jewish communal life (3). I then examine broader factors reshaping the religious landscape since reunification—including immigration from the former USSR, the role of the Hochschule für Jüdische Studien in Heidelberg, and evolving notions of Jewish identity (4). Against this backdrop, Walter Homolka emerges as a key—yet highly contested—figure in Germany’s institutional liberal Judaism (5).

The paper then details the founding of new rabbinic seminaries and the establishment of the School of Jewish Theology at the University of Potsdam (6), before turning to the crisis that destabilized these institutions (7). Through this reconstruction, I show how political culture, religious authority, and academic legitimacy intersect in the ongoing transformation of academic theology in Germany. The conclusion draws the various discussion threads together and considers the prospects of academic Jewish theology at the University of Potsdam (8).

(1) Theology as a Science & Feyerabend's Legacy

There is a long-standing debate over whether theology qualifies as a science, and if it does, what kind of science it is. This is a complex and important question, and it would be mistaken to assume it emerged only with modern science in the seventeenth century. Still, with the rise of the modern natural sciences to cultural pre-eminence in the nineteenth century, the relation between theology (understood as the study of God as a supernatural being) and the natural sciences (understood as the study of natural phenomena) has attracted most of the attention (see Brooke 1991).

Today, the application of abstract models—such as falsificationism—to determine theology's scientific status appears increasingly inadequate, largely owing to the influential contributions of Paul Feyerabend (1975). This paper forms part of a collection of papers honoring Feyerabend's enduring contribution to our understanding of science, with particular attention to the topic of pluralism and its relevance to the interaction between theology and science. I examine a recent tumult at the School of Jewish Theology at the University of Potsdam as a key cultural phenomenon that, I argue, warrants analysis for the way it illuminates the entangled epistemic and cultural-political processes shaping academic Jewish theology in contemporary Germany. To be very clear, this paper is not an exercise in Feyerabend exegesis. Rather, it aims to show how Feyerabend's critique of science, together with his insistence on historical and institutional contextualization, compel us to transform the way we pose the question of theology as a science. The case of Jewish theology in Germany serves as a concrete example, exemplifying with particular clarity the entanglement of epistemic and social orders. Feyerabend's work has been pivotal in raising awareness of this entanglement. In this sense, the present analysis is intended as a homage to Feyerabend's work, especially his legacy of cultivating diversity—that is, pluralism. As Feyerabend (1978, 106) writes:

“Science does not excel because of its methods for there is no method; and it does not excel because of its results: we know what science *does*, we have not the faintest idea whether other traditions could not do *much better*. So we must find out. To find out we must let all traditions freely develop side by side as is at any rate required by the basic stipulation of a free society.”

Against this backdrop, I am interested in the various religious traditions that are being cultivated—under state sanction—in the form of a more pluralist academic theology at public universities in Germany today. The discussion of Potsdam’s School of Jewish Theology that I am about to offer is not intended to be comprehensive institutional history but rather to mark a first significant step toward a broader conversation about academic Jewish theology in post-Shoah Germany—one pertinent to the crucial question of whether theology continues to qualify as a science and thus warrants its ongoing presence at public universities. My approach seeks to reframe the question of theology’s scientific status from an abstract and essentialist problem into a contextual and practice-oriented inquiry aligned with developments in science studies that are, in great part, indebted to Feyerabend’s legacy.

Following Sheila Jasanoff’s (2005) understanding of political culture, I regard collective decision-making as shaped by empirical and cognitive consideration, by implicit social conventions and cultural repertoires, and by formal institutional rules. From this perspective, the case of the School of Jewish Theology may be read as a most intriguing site where these formal and informal dimensions of political culture intersect, shaping the epistemic and institutional conditions under which Jewish theology claims scientific legitimacy in Germany today.

In contrast, an abstract-essentialist approach employing, for example, falsificationism defines science as a system of in experimental practice testable theoretical claims, privileging the possibility of refutation over confirmation (in contrast to verificationism). Yet such accounts overlook the important historical and cultural contingency of scientific norms (which shape methods, standards of evidence, and interpretations of experimental results in the process of theory selection) and fail to explain important aspects of scientific practice; for example, how communities often resist counterevidence to theories deemed intellectually or socially compelling.

These complications underscore a broader challenge to overly general conceptions of science that pertains to the significant interaction of science and values. The ideal of a value-free

or politically pristine science has become untenable to a considerable degree (see Elliot 2022). It is now widely recognized that knowledge production depends on social infrastructures and that what counts as science is constantly negotiated, involving epistemic (simplicity, explanatory power, unification domains of phenomena in one theory, etc.) and non-epistemic values (such as social, political, and moral values). The collapse of the “fact/value dichotomy” (Putnam 2002) and the diminishing force of the demarcation problem (what is science proper and what not) underscore this significant shift (Ruphy 2016, xi).

Rather than positing a stable ‘core’ of science, there is increasing emphasis on how its boundaries are shaped by a dynamic interplay of epistemic goals, institutional structures, and political commitments. Steering (e.g., science funding), management (e.g., laboratory culture), and application (e.g., technology) are not peripheral to science but constitutive of it. In this light, the existence and legitimacy of any scientific discipline—including theology, insofar as there are grounds to expect that it can sustain its tradition as a scientific discipline—must be understood as the outcome of complex, ongoing epistemic, cultural, and political negotiations. In Feyerabend’s work, we find one of the earliest and most influential advocates for approaching science in precisely this way.

To systematize the enormously complex array of knowledge-producing practices, Philip Kitcher (2011, 91) introduces the concept of “systems of public knowledge.” He argues that any such system reflects foundational judgments about which questions are worth asking, who is authorized to speak, how contributions are certified, and how knowledge is disseminated. These normative decisions shape the institutional authority of science and influence whether disciplines such as theology can attain scientific legitimacy. From Kitcher’s perspective, theology should not be excluded from the ranks of science primarily on the grounds that its claims are false, but because its guiding values fundamentally conflict with those of the sciences and produce harmful social consequences. He argues that theology is often ethically stagnant, epistemically insulated, politically divisive, and ultimately unnecessary for the kinds of flourishing and cooperation that make a society flourish.

This paper presents academic Jewish theology in Germany as a case study to examine how foundational questions of value—such as disciplinary legitimacy, authority, and public relevance—are continually negotiated and how the answers lend scientific credibility rather independently of equally pertinent considerations of cognitive merit. The emergence of Jewish

theology as a named and institutionally embedded discipline, along with its processes of legitimation, contestation, and present-day precarity, provides a revealing lens on the shifting place of academic theology within a secularizing, pluralist democracy. I certainly do not wish to overstate the significance of this case and the merits of my analysis in this paper. At the same time, I do think that the developments discussed in this paper represent significant cultural events that merits careful and extensive analysis. What follows can only gesture toward some of its most salient dimensions—a first step in the right direction, I hope.

I cannot stress enough that the aim of this paper is not to evaluate, judge, or attribute culpability to any individual actors. Rather, my analysis concerns the institutional, cultural, and epistemic conditions that made certain actions possible, intelligible, and publicly meaningful within Germany's system of public knowledge. The focus lies squarely on structures, norms, and processes—not on personal conduct or alleged wrongdoing. The emergence of Jewish theology as a named and institutionally embedded discipline—its legitimation, contestation, and present fragility—provides a particularly revealing vantage point for examining the evolving role of academic theology within a secularizing and pluralist democracy. By attending to institutional dynamics rather than individual motives, the paper seeks to illuminate broader patterns in the governance of knowledge, academic authority, and public trust.

Judaism, like science, resists reduction to an abstract essence. As Noah J. Efron (2007, 7) aptly notes, “if one wishes to understand the relationship between Judaism and science, the first thing to grasp is that there is no such thing as Judaism and no such thing as science”—at least not in the sense of timeless, unchanging entities. The complications extend to the very question of whether there can be such a thing as a Jewish theology, or whether confessional theology—by contrast to philosophical theology as first articulated by Plato—is a specifically Christian invention of the medieval and early modern periods, subsequently imposed upon other religious traditions.

Rather than rely solely on the findings of an abstract-general approach to science, conceptual analysis, and speculative metaphysics to understand the place of Jewish theology in society today, it is therefore instructive to examine the institutional status of Jewish theology within academia. Universities are important actors in this regard, as they function as epistemic gatekeepers: they both reflect and shape what a society recognizes as science. In the medieval university, for example, theology stood above the liberal arts as the capstone discipline (*sacra*

doctrina), known as *regina scientiarum* (“queen of the sciences”). Equally significant for present purposes is that “German universities were notoriously anti-Semitic,” as rightly noted by Gross (1999, 35)—an important consideration in understanding, for example, the history of theology at the Johann Wolfgang Goethe University in Frankfurt am Main (see Hammerstein 2015).

Unlike the traditional German model with four classical faculties—Theology, Law, Medicine, and Philosophy—Frankfurt was deliberately founded without a theological faculty. Although some Christian contemporaries advocated for the establishment of a Christian theological faculty at the new university—while explicitly warning of the “damage” a Jewish theological faculty would allegedly cause (see Wiese 1999, 339)—none of these proposals were implemented. And *that* is precisely the point I am making. This omission was intentional and symbolic: it reflected both the secular, liberal, and pluralist ideals of the city’s bourgeois sponsors and a desire to create a modern, inclusive university free from confessional dominance. The absence of theology was partly motivated by the goal of preventing religious discrimination, particularly against Jews, who were systematically excluded from theological faculties and many civil service positions in Imperial Germany.

Frankfurt, with its large and influential Jewish community, was a center of Jewish intellectual and civic life. Wealthy Jewish patrons such as the Rothschilds, Speyers, and Simon family were key founders and benefactors of the university. They envisioned a university open to Jews, Protestants, and Catholics alike—and to secular scholars—without religious barriers. In that sense, the lack of a theology faculty was a gesture of emancipation and equality: theology was seen as a site of exclusion, and its omission ensured academic freedom and neutrality in matters of religion. We are touching here on an intriguing form of secularization—one motivated not by the displacement of religion by science, but by respect for religious diversity, the pursuit of Jewish emancipation, and an awareness of discrimination on religious grounds within a pluralist society.

Today, displacement models of secularization have lost traction (see Berger 2014), and theology is once again appreciated as a formative force in modernity (see Habermas 2023). In this light, it seems prudent to approach the transformation of theology at German universities with caution, resisting the tendency to frame it simply as a decline driven by secularization. My particular interest lies in how universities—as institutional agents—either enable or constrain theology’s development, often in unintended ways.

As Gijsbert van den Brink (2020, 1) notes, “we have seen a parting of the ways of the theological discipline and public universities in many places throughout Western Europe.” Even in countries with longstanding theological traditions, theology is often perceived as a discipline in decline (see British Academy 2019). Germany remains something of an outlier: academic theology continues to be structurally embedded in public universities, though not without controversy.

This paper examines a particularly instructive case: the institutionalization of Jewish theology in Germany, both in name and in self-understanding. This development is striking not only when viewed against the backdrop of the Shoah and a rising secularization and concurrent religious diversification of German civil society, but also in light of Judaism’s aforementioned historically critical posture toward the very notion of Jewish theology (see Diamond 2018). The skeptics of Jewish theology point to Judaism’s emphasis on *orthopraxis* over *orthodoxy*—right action rather than codified belief—as a challenge to the very notion of theology within the Jewish tradition. This emphasis adds further complexity to the emergence of Jewish theology as an academic discipline—in addition to Germany’s unique post-Shoah context, but also amid Germany’s rapid secularization and simultaneous increase in religious diversity. As I will show, yet additional complications arise from political negotiations within German Jewry, within Germany’s broader system of public knowledge, and within the local context of the university itself.

Following Sheila Jasanoff (2005, 21), I take seriously the idea that political culture, understood as “the systematic means by which a political community makes binding collective choices,” is enacted not only through “institutionally sanctioned modes of action” but also through “the myriad unwritten codes and practices with which a polity supplements its formal methods of assuring accountability and legitimacy.”

Jasanoff uses this concept to explain how different political cultures produce divergent policies around the same biotechnologies across national contexts. In Germany, the legacy of the Nazi era plays a particularly significant role in shaping its distinctive approach to biotechnology, according to Jasanoff (2005). This historical sensitivity is also a key factor in understanding the genealogy of the institutionalization of Jewish theology in Germany. It helps explain the appeal of the narrative advanced by Walter Homolka (2015), who claims that the rupture caused by the Nazi regime has been symbolically repaired: the pre-Shoah vision of *Wissenschaft des*

Judentums, enjoying equal footing with Christian theology has, he argues, been realized in the establishment of Potsdam’s “School of Jewish Theology.”

This paper seeks to bring some of the dynamics to light which are highlighted by Jasanoff’s notion of political culture and in consequence moves beyond a mere analysis of policy recommendations—such as those issued in 2010 by the *Wissenschaftsrat*, which advised that academic theology should remain within Germany’s public universities rather than be relegated to confessional colleges, and that its institutional presence even be expanded to include faith traditions beyond Christianity (see Wissenschaftsrat 2010; and Homolka, Walter, and Pöttering 2013).

While not a comprehensive institutional history, this paper focuses on a major sequence of developments centered on a key figure and the recent affair in which that figure became embroiled. In doing so, it draws exclusively on publicly accessible documents, media reports, official statements, and scholarly literature; no confidential or non-public material is used. The paper does not advance, adjudicate, or endorse any allegations of misconduct, illegality, or other wrongdoing, nor does it attempt to determine individual intent or responsibility. Its discussion of events is purely descriptive and contextual, aimed at clarifying how institutional structures, norms, and power relations shaped developments surrounding the School of Jewish Theology at the University of Potsdam (hereafter SJT). The analysis reconstructs important facets of the formation of the SJT, examines the roles of some of the principal actors as they appear in the public discourse, and analyzes the tensions between state authorities, communal organizations, and academic norms that have shaped Jewish theology within the German university system.

For reasons of transparency, I note that in the course of this research I have submitted several freedom-of-information applications to relevant authorities in Germany and the United Kingdom and have lodged related appeals concerning access to information. I have also signed a public open letter, initiated by Professor Jonathan Schorsch, calling on King’s College London to investigate the allegations of plagiarism concerning Walter Homolka’s 1992 dissertation, as it was requested by the University of Potsdam, which employs Homolka as a tenured professor. These actions are undertaken solely in my capacity as a scholar, with the aim of clarifying institutional processes and practices. Apart from these information-access proceedings and the open letter, I am not a party to any other administrative, disciplinary, or legal proceedings involving the individuals or institutions discussed in this paper.

(2) Academic theology at German universities

Traditionally anchored within the public university system and supported by state funding (see, e.g., Howard 2006), theology in Germany has long operated under a unique model of cooperation between mostly Christian communities and the state (see, e.g., Heckel 1986, 1987). In recent decades, however, this arrangement has come under increasing strain—due to intensifying secularization (and related decrease in student enrolment and significance and public acceptance), constitutional commitments to worldview neutrality (not favoring the religious tradition of Christianity that considerably shaped the constitution of the state), and the significant diversification of religious identities and communities (especially the growth of the Muslim population, but also of the Jewish population). These developments have begun to reshape the institutional forms and public legitimacy of theological scholarship in considerable ways (see, e.g., Marksches 2020). The establishment of SJT is a case in point.

To be unequivocally clear from the outset: the existence of academic Jewish theology in Germany is not a recent development. What is new—and contentious—is the explicit assertion of Jewish theology by name, along with the establishment of SJT, which obviously seeks to model itself on the Christian theological faculties found at German universities. Particularly striking is the adoption of divisions such as that between “systematic” and “practical” theology—a distinction that has become increasingly untenable even within traditional frameworks like Roman Catholic theology (see Bauer 2022).

While the interdisciplinary field of Jewish studies has long been part of the German academy, the establishment of Jewish theology by name and self-orientation as a university discipline—most notably through SJT—marks a novel and not only politically most significant development. With the founding of SJT in the fall of 2013, the academic discipline of Jewish theology was established for the first time at a European university (see Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, p. 74).

At Potsdam “Jewish theology is how Judaism talks about God” (Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, p. 677; unless stated otherwise, translations from German into English are mine). At least on paper, the “Ständige Studienkommission für das Jüdisch-Geistliche Amt” (The Curricular Commission hereafter) at SJT oversees the academic and professional standards for rabbinic and cantorial training in the tradition of the liberal/reform and conservative branches of

Judaism. At the time of writing, it remains unclear whether a Curricular Commission has existed as a formally constituted body since the establishment of the SJT, or who, if anyone, has served or currently serves as its members. A freedom of information application is pending in this matter. The Curricular Commission is meant to ensure alignment with the requirements of the “Allgemeine Rabbinerkonferenz” (General Conference of Rabbis hereafter) and affiliated bodies in the academic study of “the Jewish religion, its sources, its teachings, its legal principles, its history, and its cultural currents. Its core areas are the history of the Jewish religion, biblical theology, rabbinic theology, systematic theology, philosophy of religion, religious law, and practical theology” (Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, p. 800). In teaching and research, everything may be considered, all sources studied, but not all talk about God is sanctioned. By its very constitution, academic standards and genuinely religious norms go hand in hand in determining which talk of God is permissible, acceptable, and legitimate at SJT. As envisioned, the Curricular Commission is meant to anchor academic theology in the religious community it is intended to serve.

As indicated earlier, from a traditional standpoint, the arrangement at the SJT may be regarded as problematic. These concerns should also resonate—albeit differently—within liberal Jewish frameworks, for liberal/reform Judaism has not discarded the Jewish tradition but rather reconfigured its relationship to it. The very notion of “*Jewish theology*” as an academic discipline presupposes to some extent a conceptual framework—systematic and doctrinal—that originates in Christian intellectual history (see Harrison 2015; a work that problematizes this development even with respect to Christianity for the consequences on Christianity’s contemporary relationship with modern science). This is troubling because it risks subjecting divine discourse and halakhic authority to institutional and methodological norms external to the rabbinic tradition, thereby transforming what, in Judaism, has historically been lived as covenantal praxis into a form of theoretical knowledge.

Firm objection to a Jewish Theology finds strong support in the work of Rabbi Joseph B. Soloveitchik, for example, who offers an image of Judaism that is irreconcilable with the idea of a systematic “*Jewish theology*.” For Soloveitchik, Judaism is a form of knowledge and life constituted by divine command, study, and practice, not by doctrinal synthesis. The attempt to render Judaism “theological” in the academic sense, he warns, misconstrues both its epistemic foundations and its lived normativity. As Kaplan (1973, 59) observes, even such “major

theological topics as God, revelation, [and] providence, while touched upon tangentially, never receive systematic treatment” in Soloveitchik’s work.

As Fisch (2017) has emphasised, the rationality of Jewish tradition is anchored not in systematic dogmatics but in the practices of halakhic deliberation, dispute, and self-critique, which characteristically proceed without a central authority. From this perspective, objections to the notion of “Jewish theology” are not simply conservative resistance to modernization but arise from a distinct internal understanding of how normative and self-critical reflection ought to be conducted within Judaism. Such a self-understanding coheres with the widely noted fact that Judaism lacks a universally binding creed, despite repeated attempts to formulate one (see De Lange 2000, 64, 78). On this view, Judaism is a faith community united primarily by a commitment to right action rather than assent to a fixed set of dogmas or “right belief” (see Fackenheim 1987, 73, 129, 157). In short, the difficulty with the notion of “Jewish theology” is that the concept of “theology” itself emerged largely within Christian frameworks oriented around credal formulations—propositional truths treated as intrinsically authoritative and worthy of assent—an orientation that sits uneasily with the predominantly halakhic and narrative modes of reasoning characteristic of much of Jewish tradition.

It is therefore crucial to clarify the methodological orientation of this paper. I am not offering a conceptual history of “Jewish theology.” Of course, the term was used in the nineteenth century by figures such as Abraham Geiger and in institutions like the “Jüdisch-Theologisches Seminar” in Breslau. My argument, however, concerns a different question: whether the contemporary German state’s institutionalization of *theology* as an academic category—modeled on Christian precedents—aligns with Jewish normative structures and modes of reasoning. The issue at stake is not whether the term “Jewish theology” has historical precedents, but whether the current institutional configuration genuinely corresponds to the forms of knowledge, authority, and practice that have characterized Judaism historically. It would be profoundly mistaken to dismiss such questions as mere bias toward Orthodox Judaism. Reform Judaism, too, is committed to Jewish tradition, even if it construes and develops that tradition in different ways; it therefore also has a stake in asking whether “theology,” as institutionally configured in contemporary Germany, does justice to Judaism’s normative and epistemic structures.

An agreement, “dated July 5, 2013” between the University of Potsdam and the “Union Progressiver Juden in Deutschland”—which asserts to represent in Germany the “liberal/reform”

tradition of Judaism—, and “Masorti Deutschland e.V.”—which asserts to represent in Germany the “conservative” tradition of Judaism—, “regulates the participatory and objection rights of the” Curricular Commission with respect to curriculum and faculty appointments (Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, p. 79).

The appointment of a faculty member at SJT, for example, is permanently conditional not only upon academic integrity, but also religious confession (“Bekenntnis”), although the faculty member might be “verbeamtet” (tenured for life), in which case the faculty member might lose the appointment at SJT but not at the University of Potsdam, on grounds of religious confession (see Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, p. 80).

Like all other academic units at German universities, theology units are publicly funded and embedded within the university. They offer research and degree programs (including BA, MA, and PhD/ThD), and are institutionally integrated into the otherwise secularized university system. What makes them unique is that, by their very constitution, these units reserve extensive rights over curriculum and faculty appointments to non-academic groups that are external to the university system, namely state-recognized religious communities. They operate under legal arrangements that reflect Germany’s unique model of positive religious neutrality (worldview neutrality) and cooperation between the state and state-recognized religious communities, such as the Roman-Catholic Church. This arrangement has many benefits for the state and the religious communities. But it can also create enormous tensions and challenges.

For example, the archbishop of Cologne, Cardinal Klaus Maria Woelki has established a theological school in Cologne—financed by the Archdiocese of Cologne (which is among the wealthiest diocese globally). By legal agreement with the state, however, the academic training of the archdiocese’s future clergy is at the University of Bonn, which has a Catholic theological faculty, fully funded by the state and with numerous tenured professors appointed, permanently conditional upon approval by the archdiocese and the Vatican. Therefore, the state has threatened Woelki with a breach-of-contract procedure at the Vatican (see Welt 2022).

Meanwhile, another conflict has been brewing—at SJT. The German weekly newspaper *Die Zeit* published an interview with Rabbi Andreas Nachama (born in 1951 in Berlin) in the fall of 2024. Rabbi Nachama is being interviewed in his capacity as the rabbinic principal of the Abraham Geiger Kolleg (AGK hereafter), which is a rabbinic and cantorial seminary in the tradition of liberal/reform Judaism, whose students receive their academic training at SJT. In the

interview, he voiced the suspicion that “the Central Council [of Jews in Germany, YF] wants to be the supreme authority for all Jewish matters in Germany. As a predominantly conservative and Orthodox organization,” Nachama alleges, it “seeks to exert control over liberal Judaism in the future. This includes the Potsdam rabbinical seminary [i.e., AGK, YF] and the Jewish Community of Berlin [which, at the time of the interview, was in open dispute with the Central Council over its authority regarding the rabbinic seminary and other significant matters, YF].” What the Central Council of Jews intends thereby, Nachama claims, is “to enforce its claim to sole representation — and the ministries are going along with it. Over the past nine months, all my attempts to speak with the [federal, YF] Ministry for Interior Affairs [which had been a sponsor of the AGK, YF] about our situation [at the AGK, YF] have failed because I was told: We have decided in favor of the Central Council.”

Nachama’s striking contention is highly relevant to the present discussion, as the SJT is a product of liberal/reform Judaism and deeply rooted in the AGK. The Central Council of Jews is portrayed by Nachama as an adversary of liberal Judaism in virtue of the Council’s preference for traditional Judaism, and thus positioned as a threat to the AGK—one of the pillars of SJT.

(3) “Non-observant Orthodoxy” in Germany after the Shoa

The Central Council of Jews is a political entity, not a central religious authority, established in 1950 to provide a basic infrastructure that sustains an integrated communal Jewish life locally and nationwide. It functions as an umbrella organization serving Jewish communities across Germany, representing them publicly, advocating on their behalf, and negotiating with the state on matters such as funding and security. Both “regional associations” (Landesverbände) and local Jewish communities of a larger size are members of the Central Council. The local communities are organized as “united communities” (*Einheitsgemeinden*) that seek to “house under one roof”, as it were, the various denominations of Judaism, partly on the basis of the assumption that there aren’t enough Jews in Germany to justify the existence of various independent local Jewish communities. Although the institutional roots of the “Einheitsgemeinde” model can be traced back to Prussian regulations in the 19th century, the form it took after 1945 was fundamentally reconfigured. The post-Shoah “Einheitsgemeinde” was not a continuation of the Prussian administrative structure but a new institutional arrangement shaped by the catastrophic demographic rupture of the Shoah, the need to rebuild

communal life with very small numbers, and the postwar political framework of Jewish-state relations. My concern is with its post-Shoah reinterpretation as an institutional mechanism for government recognition and funding of Jewish communities.

According to Micha Brumlik (1995, 215), after German reunification in 1990 the small neo-Orthodox community “Adass Yisroel” insisted on continuing to exist independently and thereby “successfully challenged the principle of the” post-Shoah form of the “united community,” a move that “earned the community the ostracism and hostility of the other Jewish communities.” To this day, “Adass Yisroel” is not a member of the Central Council of Jews and enjoys recognition by the state as a public corporation (“Körperschaft des öffentlichen Rechts”, or “K.d.ö.R.”, which is established by statute to perform public duties, endowed with certain sovereign rights such as self-governance and the ability to levy fees or contributions). Other Jewish communities followed in its path of independence—many of them anything but Orthodox in their theological orientation.

The “united community” of Hamburg, for example, encompasses two synagogues, each with its own clergy. There is also an independent liberal Jewish community that resists integration into the “united community” of Hamburg and demands independent and equal recognition from the state. Legally, it is the successor of the very first liberal community ever, and this explains its somewhat antiquated sounding name: “Israelite Temple Association of Hamburg, founded in 1817 / Liberal Jewish Community of Hamburg.” De facto, Hamburg has two synagogues in the “liberal/reform” tradition—one inside the “united community” and one outside of it.

The current rabbi of the independent liberal community, Alina Treiger, is a graduate of the AGK. She was ordained in 2010 as the first female rabbi in Germany since the Shoah. Among her predecessors was Rabbi Daniel Alter, a member of the first cohort of AGK graduates to receive ordination in 2006—the first such ordinations in Germany since the Shoah. Surprisingly, this community has yet to receive state recognition as a public corporation (as defined). To be clear, it is recognized by the state as a religious community (which basically means, in legal terms, that the state may cooperate with it, despite state’s constitutional obligation to maintain neutrality regarding worldviews), but the granting of public corporation status does not necessarily follow from that.

The leadership of the Central Council of Jews includes a President, Vice Presidents, and an Executive Committee (Präsidium), elected by a general assembly (Ratstag). While it represents on the order of 90,000–100,000 affiliated Jews today, the Central Council of Jews does not represent many secular Jews and Jews who have no membership in any community, nor those who have elected to organize themselves outside the Central Council, such as the “Israelite Temple Association of Hamburg, founded in 1817 / Liberal Jewish Community of Hamburg.”

Nevertheless, the Central Council of Jews remains the most visible and influential representative body of Jews in Germany at the national level. It is recognized as a public corporation (as defined), and has negotiated state treaties (Staatsverträge) with the federal government and individual Länder (federal states), guaranteeing funding and rights comparable to those granted to the state-recognized two major Christian churches of Roman-Catholics and Protestant-Lutherans, which together used to make up 95% of the population in Germany in the 1950s, although by now, the number has gone down to less than 50%!.

According to Uri R. Kaufmann (1995, 37), the council’s “claim to represent the community” as a whole began to “erode” palpably in the 1990s. An important part of that development concerned opposition to a peculiar understanding and practice of Judaism as it had developed since the 1950s in Germany. There was a “monolithic-orthodox image projected to the outside (with no basis in real life),” Kaufmann (1995, 32–33) explains. For example, not a few members in most of the few “united communities” across Germany did not “practice orthodoxy in their day-to-day lives, and this has led to the peculiar phenomenon of ‘non-observant Orthodoxy’ in Germany,” because, as Brumlik (1995, 212) observes, after the Shoah, “it was most important to restore a familiar environment, a form of religious identity as well as places in which community could be fostered. In practice, this meant that primarily moderate Orthodox rites were cultivated in the communities.

The situation revealed a paucity of imagination for Jewish life (maybe combined with the German-Prussian mentality of aiming for perfection while falling short), surely shaped by the trauma of the Shoah and the small number of Jews living in Germany (spread all over the country in a fragmented way with the exception of a few big cities, such as Munich and Frankfurt) after 1950 (once the thousands of displaced persons of Jewish identity had left Germany). Brumlik (1995, 214) notes “an unimaginative repetition” of the familiar and a

profound “spiritual shortcoming” over the decades from the 1950s to the 1990s. Wolffsohn (1995, 135) explains that “German Judaism” had been “emptied of its religious substance.”

The familiar tripartite schema of Jewish religious currents—Liberal/Reform, Positive-Historical (later called Conservative), and Orthodox—is commonly *retrospectively* traced back to nineteenth-century German Jewry and associated with the rabbis Abraham Geiger (Reform/Liberal), Zacharias Frankel (Positive-Historical/Conservative), and Samson Raphael Hirsch (Orthodoxy) (see only Lebrecht 2020). In the late twentieth century, however, this denominational map no longer functioned well to describe Jewish religious life in post-Shoah Germany, according to Kaufman (1995, 31). In 1995, “only one of the 12 ‘officially’ installed rabbis” was “liberal and only one conservative.” The relatively secular community in Frankfurt “even went so far as to call in a Hasidic rabbi from Bene Beraq (Israel).” And in Munich, there were “three Orthodox rabbis.” At the time, “the great majority of the Jews in Germany—probably two-thirds of some 40,000—” lived in six big cities, Kaufman (1995) notes, namely “Berlin, Frankfurt, Munich, Düsseldorf, Cologne, and Hamburg.”

(4) The changing landscape of Jewish life in Germany

Pressure on the prevalent ‘non-observant Orthodoxy’ grew considerably during the 1990s. First, the younger generation had its own ideas about Jewish identity, drawing both inspiration and resources from Jewish life in the United States. They were “searching for forms of religious identity that” corresponded to their lifestyle as Jews in a modern society like Germany. It is only against this background,” Brumlik (2014, 216) argues, that one can understand the controversies” that erupted in the 1990s “in several Jewish communities” such as in Heidelberg where “women refused to take their seats in the gallery” of the synagogue separated from the men.

Second, through the work of the Hochschule für Jüdische Studien in Heidelberg (hereafter HfJS) (established in 1979) an informed (progressive) influence on Jewish life in Germany emerged—an impact may be comparable to that exercised by non-Orthodox rabbis who had been ordained abroad and returned to Germany to build alternative communities (not to mention the progressive American Jews who moved to Germany). The HfJS was founded with the intention of reviving Jewish scholarship in Germany, inspired by the tradition of the “Wissenschaft des Judentums” (The Science of Judaism, as envisioned first by the German Jewish scholar,

historian, and one of the leading figures of the Jewish Enlightenment (Haskalah), Leopold Zunz; see Meyer 1967).). The original vision for HfJS was to provide an education to satisfy the needs of the Jewish community in Germany, including the training of rabbis, cantors, and religious educators.

The impact of the HfJS must not be overstated, however, since the institution evolved into a broader academic center for Jewish Studies, open to students of all backgrounds. This shift led to some criticism, notably from Rabbi Nathan Peter Levinson (born 1921 in Berlin and passed away in 2016 there), who lamented in his 1996 memoirs that the HfJS had failed in its mission to serve the Jewish communities in Germany, calling it a rabbinic seminary for Christians (see Levinson 1996).

Third, as tens of thousands of Jews from the former USSR were admitted to Germany—and as many young Israelis of German descent sought new opportunities in a reunified and significantly transformed Berlin (and elsewhere in Germany)—the Jewish community underwent a seismic shift. “The integration of these people into the Jewish communities,” Brumlik (1995, 215) notes, posed “a not inconsiderable problem” and this for several reasons. First, they began to outnumber the existing Jews. Second, there was little inclination to perpetuate a Jewish culture of “a non-observant Orthodoxy.” Third, many new communities emerged, and this required substantial changes to the existing infrastructure for Jewish life across Germany. Most importantly for present purposes is that many new (but also the established) Jewish communities needed clergy, and this practical demand converged with an ideological desire to recreate the vibrant, pluralist Jewish life that had existed on German soil before 1933.

Hannah Tzuberi (2020) uses the notion of *Wiederaufforstung* (“reforestation”; evoking the image of six million lost Jewish lives as felled trees) to describe the German state’s efforts to rebuild Jewish life after the Shoah—particularly through the immigration of Jews from the former Soviet Union—aimed more at restoring a symbolic Jewish presence for the sake of Germany’s post-Shoah self-image than at fostering genuine Jewish continuity on its own terms. This structural reading does not exclude other, more actor-centered accounts—such as those that emphasize the initiative of émigré liberal Jewish leaders and early dependence on private donations in the founding of institutions like the AGK—but it helps to illuminate why such initiatives could resonate so powerfully with state actors in the in post-Shoah reunited Germany. If that analysis is correct, then it is surely reasonable to surmise that the combination of acute

needs for clergy and training of religious leaders and the state program of “reforestation” proved politically extremely powerful—and one individual, in particular, was able to capitalize on it—Walter Homolka (born 1964 in Landau an der Isar).

Homolka has been a prominent and frequently discussed figure within the Jewish landscape in Germany, and various public controversies associated with his career have shaped the way he has been perceived in national and communal discourse. In this paper, I treat these publicly reported episodes not as evidence of personal conduct, but as cultural events through which certain currents of political culture—understood in Jasanoff’s (2005) sense and as clarified earlier—can be discerned. Within the framework of this paper’s aims, they constitute cultural phenomena for analysis precisely because they exemplify negotiations on the plane of political culture along two interrelated axes developed thus far. The first is the axis of negotiation between differing forms and self-understandings of Judaism, which raises corresponding questions about the very possibility of a “Jewish theology.” The second is the axis of negotiation concerning the identity of post-Shoah Germany and the symbolic role accorded to Jewish institutions in that process. In the publicly mediated figure of Homolka, these two axes intersect in ways that illuminate dynamics unlikely to appear with equal clarity in other contexts.

(5) “Dr. Walter Homolka is neither a rabbi nor a Jew.”

Homolka faced stern opposition from the Central Council of Jews and other institutions in its close vicinity, such as the Conference of Rabbis, whose members were (mostly) employed by the “united communities” which were financed by the council (using allocated state funds).

On January 22, 1998, Rabbi Joel Berger issued an announcement on behalf of the Conference of Rabbis stating that its members had reached the unanimous decision that “Dr. Walter Homolka is neither a rabbi nor a Jew.” As the provenance of sources is crucial in this context, I note that I possess a PDF copy of a fax containing the handwritten text of this announcement. This document was provided to me by Professor Jonathan Schorsch of the SJT upon my request and appears to have reached him originally from Dr. Michael Fürst—head of the Regional Council of Jews in Lower Saxony—as part of a broader set of materials relating to Homolka. For the sake of clarity, I refer to this set of documents as the “Fürst Package” hereafter. A public reference to the announcement appears in Krampitz (2023). However, it remains unclear to me to whom the announcement was addressed, what its intended audience or

status was, and whether it was ever released as a public or official statement. In citing the document, I do not make any claim about the accuracy of its content, its legal significance, or its intended scope; I discuss it solely as part of the documentary and discursive record relevant to my scholarly treatment of the various public controversies associated with the career path of Homolka.

Such an announcement as Rabbi Berger's may seem utterly inappropriate, since, from the perspective of many Jewish ethical and halakhic traditions, publicly declaring an individual "neither a rabbi nor a Jew" is itself highly problematic, whatever one's assessment of the person's conduct. It implicates questions of communal responsibility and the limits of public delegitimization. Germany is a unique context, however, as illustrated by a similarly problematic episode involving another rabbi. According to Axelrod (2007), a significant controversy arose in 2007 when Rabbi Gesa Ederberg, then the newly appointed and first female community rabbi in Berlin at the New Synagogue on Oranienburger Straße (affiliated with the Conservative movement), referred to Berlin's senior Orthodox rabbi, Yitzchak Ehrenberg—who was physically present—as her "colleague."

In a letter—to which I have had no access and thus rely on the information available in the press—to the head of the Jewish community Berlin, which employs them both, Rabbi Yitzchak Ehrenberg made it clear, as reported, that he felt publicly shamed by this speech act and found his reputation tarnished, because he considers Rabbi Ederberg to be neither a rabbi (probably because she is part of the Conservative branch of Judaism) nor a Jew for that matter (probably because she was admitted to the Jewish people by a rabbinic court of the Conservative branch of Judaism).

The decision of the Conference of Rabbis in the case of Homolka about a decade earlier was supported by Rabbi Ernst Max Stein, who had admitted him into the Jewish community sixteen years earlier in 1982. Stein's was the only liberal Jewish community in (West-) Germany at the time. Probably as a surprise to Stein and his colleagues, in 1992, Homolka obtained a PhD in Christian theology from King's College London (KCL, hereafter), which he celebrated on May 2, 1993, in form of a Protestant-Lutheran religious service in Munich, in which, on top of it, he even delivered a Christian-trinitarian sermon—a copy of which is part of the "Fürst Package. The written text of the sermon begins with the words: "Gnade sei mit euch von Gott, unserem Vater, und seinem Sohn, unserem Herrn Jesus Christus, der regiert in der Einheit mit dem

heiligen Geiste”— Grace be with you from God, our Father, and his Son, our Lord Jesus Christ, who reigns in unity with the Holy Spirit.

These religious actions must have raised questions about the sincerity of Homolka’s intention, in 1982, to become part of the Jewish people. And yet, there is evidence of sincerity; after admission into the Jewish community, Homolka had registered as a Jew with the Straubinger Jüdische Gemeinde in April 1982, and in 1984 he had organized the liberal “Chavura Or Chadash” in Munich. During his studies in Protestant theology in Munich— studies undertaken in preparation for admission to Leo Baeck College (LBC hereafter), I surmise—he had written a thesis on a genuinely Jewish topic: the use of midrash in the Pesach Haggadah. All of this important information about the years after Homolka’s admission into the Jewish community in 1982, I was able to draw from a report by Rabbi Levinson, which I found included in the “Fürst Package”; I do not know for whom the report was written or for what purpose it was created; probably to inform the deliberations that took place at the Conference of Rabbis. In any case, I couldn’t confirm the information contained in Levinson’s report independently.

In parts of the public and communal discourse, some critics have characterized Homolka as a “religious opportunist,” alleging that he changes his religious affiliation when doing so appears advantageous. I cite this characterization here solely as part of the documented controversy surrounding him and do not endorse or assess its accuracy. In any case, rather than viewing Homolka’s complex religious vita as indicative of a personal struggle with faith, the Conference of Rabbis must have interpreted it as strong evidence against the sincerity of his intention to become a Jew in 1982. In doing so, it seems either to have discounted, or perhaps simply not to have been aware of, materials suggesting that his actions immediately after conversion pointed toward a serious commitment to Jewish life. In any event, this was not the only complication surrounding Homolka’s position within the Jewish community at the outset of what would become his highly influential role in developing liberal Judaism and, later, in helping to establish academic Jewish theology in Germany by name and in unprecedented institutional form in Potsdam.

In 1997 Homolka had received a private ordination by Rabbi Walter Jacobs in Pittsburgh, which the US Central Council of American Rabbis (CCAR hereafter) refused to recognize, however, and this despite the fact that Jacobs enjoyed considerable authority in the CCAR as

chairman of the “Responsa Committee” from 1967 until 1990. From 1991 to 1993 he even served as its president. The reason for CCAR’s refusal to recognize Homolka’s ordination, is probably not a judgment about Homolka’s religious character, nor the mere fact that he became a rabbi through private ordination—as always claimed in the press—but more likely the fact that there is lack of evidence that Homolka “successfully completed an extended and rigorous program of Torah study and professional training,” which is deemed a necessary requirement for recognition as a rabbi by the CCAR, according to CCAR Reform Responsa RR21 no. 5759.3.

Homolka did desire to become a Rabbi all along, it seems, since there is public evidence that he enrolled in a rabbinic training program at LBC in 1986. In the “Fürst Package” is a copy of an article published on page 40 in the *Deutsches Allgemeines Sonntagsblatt* and dated January 2, 1998, entitled: “Porträt: Walter Homolka: Der Öko Rabbi,” which contains the following sentence: “Nach der Ordination durch das Leo Baeck College führte ihn im Sommer 1997 die liberal jüdische Gemeinde Beth Shalom in München in das Amt eines Rabbiners ein”—After his ordination by the Leo Baeck College, the liberal Jewish congregation Beth Shalom in Munich installed him in the office of rabbi in the summer of 1997.

There is public evidence that he did not complete the program at LBC, according to Schorsch 2023, who writes that an LBC faculty member reports that Homolka “came to the college with little knowledge of Judaism and was accepted on the basis that he would commit himself to the course. He didn’t wish to do so,” the LBC faculty member’s report continues, “but demanded that the College should supply him with the document without studying the required subjects and attending the required courses.” LBC didn’t comply with Homolka’s wish, we are told. “Finally, he managed to persuade a well-known American rabbi to give him the semichah,” Schorsch 2023 speculates.

In short, when Rabbi Berger issued his announcement in 1998 on behalf of the Conference of Rabbis, Homolka already occupied a highly contested and ambiguous position within the Jewish community—shaped both by his own decisions and by the actions of those who supported him. His halakhically ambiguous status, both as a Jew and as a rabbi, became the subject of sustained discussion and dispute in Jewish communal settings in Germany and, to some extent, beyond.

In a letter dated October 21, 2004, written on Central Council letterhead and personally addressed to Dr. Michael Fürst (the compiler of the “Fürst Package”), the then-president of the

Central Council, Paul Spiegel, allegedly thanked Fürst “for the extensive documents about our ‘friend’ Homolka. I share your view,” Spiegel continued, “that the time has now come to consider how we might take action against this charlatan. Best regards, Yours, Paul Spiegel.” To maintain clarity about the sources, I note that I have a PDF copy of this letter as contained in the “Fürst Package,” but I have not been able to independently verify its authenticity. There is, however, no evidence before me that would give reason to doubt it. Nor was I able to clarify the specific circumstances under which the letter was written—for example, whether it was related to contemporaneous rumours that the President of Germany was considering awarding Homolka a high order (Homolka did receive the Federal Cross of Merit, First Class, in 2015)—or to confirm with certainty which “extensive documents” are referenced, although it is reasonable to assume that they correspond to materials now contained in the “Fürst Package.” I cite the letter here solely as part of the documentary record and do not endorse or adopt the characterizations it contains.

In this exchange, the president of the Central Council of Jews expresses strong appreciation to the chairman of one of the regional associations of Jewish “united communities” for compiling documents on Homolka, and indicates that, in his view, the time had come to consider taking action against him—going so far as to refer to him as a “charlatan.” This took place in 2004, by which time Homolka (with the support of others) had already established the AGK and signed agreements with the University of Potsdam to train “liberal/reform” rabbis and cantors (see Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, p. 43). The first cohort graduated and received ordination in 2006, with the backing of an institution central to organizing “liberal/reform” Jewish life in Germany, the Union of Progressive Jews (UpJ, founded in 1999).

Viewed from the perspective of these developments alone, the level of concern expressed in the exchange is difficult to account for. Even taking into consideration the ambiguous and contested halakhic position Homolka had assumed within parts of the Jewish community, the reaction appears, at least *prima facie*, unusually strong. Halakhic questions regarding his status as both Jew and rabbi, by themselves, seem insufficient to explain the intensity of the language employed, suggesting that additional factors—communal, political, or institutional—may have been at play.

Instructive in that regard are the more nuanced reactions by other influential stakeholders in Germany’s Jewish community—such as Rabbi Levinson, who, while acknowledging that

some of Homolka's actions were deeply problematic and objectionable, nonetheless cautioned, on the basis of Jewish tradition, against questioning whether Homolka is a Jew or a rabbi. The "Fürst Package" includes a transcript of a radio segment by Robert Hübsaat discussing the controversy surrounding Homolka, broadcast on March 30, 1998, on the public channel NDR 4, which contains original quotations attributed to Rabbi Levinson and on which I rely. Unfortunately, I have not been able to locate an audio recording of the broadcast and therefore cannot independently verify the accuracy of the transcript or of Levinson's statements as reported there. There is, however, no evidence before me that would cast doubt on the transcript's reliability, and it remains a crucial source for any reconstruction of these developments, not least because it introduces cautionary halakhic deliberation into an otherwise highly politically charged situation.

(6) The "School of Jewish Theology" (SJT)

If all of this were not already perplexing enough, what is even more striking is that, despite his highly contested and ambiguous position within the Jewish community—and the considerable resistance he evidently faced from the Central Council—Homolka nonetheless prospered. In parallel, liberal and reform Judaism expanded in Germany at a remarkable pace, paving the way for the institutionalization of "Jewish theology" in the form of the SJT. The significance of this development can hardly be overstated; it is, I suspect, a case that Feyerabend himself would have found intellectually irresistible.

In 1999, the UpJ came into being. In 2020, Homolka was elected for a second time as its chairman at the UpJ's annual meeting, which, according to *Jüdische Allgemeine* (2020), counted "about 170 participants from across Germany." The UpJ is "the umbrella organization of 26 liberal congregations in Germany, with around 5,200 members." Homolka was committed to providing these communities with clergy.

When the German Council of Science and Humanities (German Council hereafter; see Wissenschaftsrat 2010) recommended in 2010 "that, whatever the religion or denomination," Homolka (2015, 197) recalls, "the training of clergy and religious leaders remain part of the public university system" instead of "encouraging religious groups and churches to found private academies and seminaries," Homolka (with the support of others) seized this unique opportunity, and began his campaign for the establishment of SJT.

Armed with the policy recommendations of the German Council and inspired by pre-Shoah visions of a Jewish theological faculty, he publicly pressured the University of Potsdam to establish a faculty of Jewish theology modeled on the existing Christian theological faculties in Germany. According to *Jüdische Allgemeine* (2011), it “sounded like an ultimatum. If a fully-fledged Jewish theological faculty is not established soon at the University of Potsdam, said Rabbi Walter Homolka, rector of the Abraham Geiger College in Potsdam, last week, they would consider an offer from the University of Erlangen-Nuremberg to move the Geiger College to Bavaria.”

An offer from the University of Erlangen-Nuremberg did not exist, according to the same newspaper article, which quotes the president of that university to that effect, although the president shows interest in such a move. The publicity that Homolka obviously meant to generate, as a negotiation strategy, I surmise, compelled the University of Potsdam and the responsible ministry in the federal state of Brandenburg to respond. The response, as reported in the press, was surprisingly positive and indicated that concrete steps were already being considered to establish “a fully-fledged Jewish theological faculty” and “in the winter semester of 2013/2014 the School of Jewish Theology at the University of Potsdam admitted the first students to study Jewish theology,” according to Homolka (2015, 198).

“The School has quasi-faculty status, with its own right to confer doctorates and its own authority to appoint professors,” as Goldman (2023) rightly notes. If Tzuberi’s (2020) “reforestation” claim is correct, then the emergence of the SJT can plausibly be understood as a uniquely fertile institutional ecosystem in which new Jewish theological initiatives could take root and flourish. A wide range of interests coalesced in its formation: (1) the aspiration, associated with Homolka, to assume a leading role within the Jewish community; (2) the University of Potsdam’s desire to strengthen its profile as a pioneer of Jewish theology in Germany and Europe; (3) the potential for growth within the university’s already substantial Jewish Studies program; (4) the federal state of Brandenburg’s aim to enhance its standing within the national university landscape—a standing closely tied to the rising reputation of the University of Potsdam; (5) liberal Judaism’s need both for institutional recognition independent of the Central Council of Jews and for the training of clergy; (6) the broader state-led effort to rebuild Jewish communal life in Germany; and (7) the attraction of an affordable rabbinic and cantorial training program—tuition-free, unlike comparable programs in the U.S.—which drew

students from abroad despite German being the language of instruction. In short, anyone who regards the SJT merely as a department of the University of Potsdam grounded in an unproblematic, self-evident “Jewish theology” risks overlooking its far-reaching cultural and political significance.

By 2013, the AGK had already existed for more than a decade, and the Jewish Studies program as it existed prior to the founding of the SJT must have served the AGK’s mission effectively, given that the AGK had been producing “liberal” rabbis before the SJT came into being. When the AGK was established, it was the first rabbinic and cantorial seminary in continental Europe founded after the Shoah (as noted earlier, the HfJS was seen as a disappointment in this regard). In 2013, a second seminary was established—also by Homolka (with the support of others)—this time affiliated with the “Conservative” movement: the Zacharias Frankel Kolleg (hereafter ZFK).

In addition to the substantial changes required at the state level for SJT to come into existence—the constitution of the federal state Brandenburg had to be changed, for instance—new agreements had to be signed to formalize the new kind of cooperation between the University of Potsdam and the AGK and the ZFK, rendering them each an “An-Institut” (affiliated institute) at the university (see Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, p. 43 and p. 68). While AGK and ZFK remain independent institutions, they are nonetheless institutionally linked to the university in various ways. For example, joint faculty appointments exist, and the rabbis and cantors in training at the two seminaries, fulfill important program requirements at the University of Potsdam. The copy of the ZFK Student Handbook, for example, as reproduced in Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, p. 672, reads: “The curriculum of Zacharias Frankel College is structured within two institutional models of graduate Jewish education: a broad spectrum of Jewish knowledge, essential for a future rabbi, which is offered in a German public university - the School of Jewish Theology at the University of Potsdam, and a specific sequence of courses and practical experiences which prepare new Masorti/ Conservative rabbis” at ZFK.

For this arrangement to succeed in achieving its goals, it must be built on a solid foundation of trust among all stakeholders, including the president and the senate of the University of Potsdam, the head of SJT, and the heads of AGK and ZFK and their *Träger* (the sponsoring body and institutional bearer, responsible as a legal person for establishing, maintaining, and legally representing an institution, bearing its rights and obligations under

public or private law)—not to mention the ministries and Jewish institutions that provide funds to finance the operation and legitimacy as an accredited theological institution. The greater a single person’s power over an entire apparatus like this, the more susceptible that apparatus becomes to collapse when the individual is compromised. SJT proved no exception.

By 2022, Homolka was “arguably the most powerful figure within German liberal Judaism” (Posener 2022). Measured by the institutions he founded and directed, the substantial support he garnered for liberal Judaism in Germany, and his success in establishing the SJT, Homolka may be considered one of the most accomplished figures in the country’s Jewish community since the Shoah. His highly contested and ambiguous position as a rabbi and Jew did not present a noticeable obstacle in that regard—nor did the opposition he faced, at times even from within the circles of liberal Judaism.

For example, Micha Brumlik, born in 1947 in Davos, Switzerland, to German-Jewish parents, and a very prominent Jewish public intellectual in Germany until his passing in 2025, stepped down as chairman of the UpJ early on in its existence, as he disagreed publicly with what he described as Homolka’s “sectarian” approach in establishing liberal Judaism at the expense of broader integration within the Jewish community in Germany. I am relying here on a newspaper article contained in the “Fürst Package” which I have been unable to locate independently and therefore cannot confirm its authenticity. I have, however, no evidence before me to doubt its authenticity. On the contrary, Brumlik’s statements are often referred to in public sources, such as Posener (2022b).

(7) A Sudden Proliferation of Rabbinic Seminaries

But since 2022, the situation has shifted dramatically for Homolka, with consequences for the cause of academic Jewish theology in Germany that yet remain difficult to fully assess in their scope and significance. This makes the case even more scholarly intriguing in the context of an assessment of the transformation of academic theology in Germany at large. Probably, nowhere is that transformation more evident than at the SJT.

Our “goal is to save Jewish theology in Germany” the press quoted the president of the University of Potsdam, Professor Oliver Günther, in the fall of 2022. “The structures should be replaced or modified. The School of Jewish Theology is part of the university.” (*Jüdische Allgemeine* 2022).

By 2022, academic Jewish theology that had just made its appearance in Germany's university system, appeared to be in urgent need of preservation, according to the president of the university which has been one of the pioneers of the development. To appreciate the gravity of the situation, it is necessary to recall that only the University of Potsdam offers a program explicitly named "Jewish Theology," and that in terms of its institutional genealogy, the primary function of SJT has been the academic training of rabbis and cantors within the "liberal" and "conservative" streams of Judaism, complementing the training that the candidates undergo at their respective seminaries (either AGK or ZFK; see Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, p. 55).

To this end, SJT comprises ten departments (disregarding the formidable Jewish Studies Department at the University of Potsdam). However, as of the time of writing, the information available on its website suggests that only two tenured professorships are based at the University of Potsdam's SJT: Professor Jonathan Schorsch (Jewish Religious and Intellectual History), and Professor Homolka (Jewish Religious Philosophy, with a focus on denominational structures and interreligious relations). This suggests a significant underrepresentation of tenured faculty relative to SJT's curriculum and mandate.

As is the case across the university sector, tenured faculty positions (and the related operational costs) are a scarce and carefully allocated resource. Whatever their academic merit or broader institutional value, and irrespective of any legal entitlements held by constituent schools, the approval of such positions often depends heavily on student enrollment figures. In this respect, enrollment in the two affiliated seminaries becomes particularly consequential, even though students (interested specifically in Jewish theology) can enroll in the program of SJT without being enrolled at AGK and ZFK. Yet, SJT itself is clearly meant to be an institution to serve a faith community and not merely Jewish Studies, which render SJT's existence contingent upon the support and recognition of key segments of the Jewish community in Germany and abroad aligned with the "liberal" and "conservative" movements, as well as upon political allies situated within state-level decision-making bodies. Homolka had secured support for SJT in that sense.

This situation changed dramatically in January 2022. A letter began to circulate within the administration of the University of Potsdam and the Ministry for Education, Research, and Culture of the federal state of Brandenburg. Its contents called Homolka's institutional role into question, contributed to a noticeable shift in the attitudes of some of his previous supporters, and

provided longstanding critics with new opportunities to argue—now with greater public resonance—for a reconfiguration of the institutional infrastructure he had helped to establish around the SJT.

It is not possible, nor would it be methodologically appropriate, for me to substantiate a linear cause-and-effect relationship between the allegations set out in the letter and the subsequent calls for institutional restructuring of the SJT. More plausibly, the developments that unfolded from 2022 onward—and that have had such considerable impact on the SJT and the Jewish community more broadly—reflect a convergence of interests and institutional logics that none of the actors involved could have fully anticipated, including the letter’s author, Professor Jonathan Schorsch.

Homolka (2022) himself resists a nuanced and balanced interpretation. Instead, he presents Schorsch’s letter as an act of personal retaliation. In Homolka’s account, in his capacity as director of the SJT he was obliged to reprimand Schorsch for allegedly spending extended periods away from Potsdam while in the United States, which he describes as a breach of duty. According to Homolka (2022), Schorsch’s letter was written in response to this reprimand. I report this explanation solely as Homolka’s own interpretation of events and take no position on its accuracy.

I have not enough evidence before to definitively rule out Homolka’s ascription of motive; however, in light of my findings to date, such an interpretation appears reductive and does not adequately account for the broader developments that have unfolded since 2022. To be clear, some of Schorsch’s public statements do convey a high degree of personal and moral criticism. In an unusually strong public statement, he described Homolka as a “self-serving, malicious, and unrepentant person [who, YF] insists that he is qualified to teach or lead anything in the Jewish community” and added that Homolka “utterly lacks the fundamental qualities required of a rabbi” (Jüdische Allgemeine 2022b). I cite these characterizations here only as part of the public record of the controversy and do not endorse or adopt them.

Homolka initiated legal proceedings against Schorsch and the *Jüdische Allgemeine* in connection with these statements (see Landgericht Frankfurt am Main, Case No. 2-03 O 343/22). The court held that Schorsch’s assessments were protected as expressions of opinion under the constitutional right to freedom of expression. It should be noted that, to date, Homolka has not been convicted of any criminal offense by a court of law.

Questions of intent are inherently difficult to assess and, in any case, are unlikely to be decisive in accounting for the broader cultural dynamics that shape the position of academic Jewish theology in Germany today, and which are primary interest for present purposes. They should not, however, obscure the substantive nature of the accusations that have been levelled against Homolka by Schorsch and numerous others since 2022.

The investigatory commission established by the president of the University of Potsdam—at the request of the Ministry for Education, Research, and Culture of the federal state of Brandenburg, and in response to the allegations contained in Schorsch’s letter (of which I myself have no copy)—organizes the accusations against Homolka into three categories. “The allegations raised in the letter from Prof. Schorsch,” the commission explains, “are varied and detailed, and pertain to three areas of investigation: First, there was the accusation of abuse of power, allegedly exercised by Prof. Homolka personally as well as through his institutional networks. Second, there was an allegation of sexual harassment of students, for which he, in collaboration with his partner, Mr. Bomhoff, was said to bear responsibility. Third, Prof. Homolka was accused of misconduct in his scholarly publications” (Universität Potsdam 2022, pp. 2–3).

According to the published report, the commission concluded that the accusations “against Prof. Homolka regarding abuse of power—through the accumulation of offices, the creation of problematic study and employment conditions, and interference in career trajectories—have so far been substantiated.” By contrast, the allegations in the second category, relating to sexual harassment, “have not been substantiated.” With respect to the third category, the commission “recommends that the allegation of academic misconduct be further examined by the university’s commission for the investigation of allegations of academic misconduct” (Universität Potsdam 2022, pp. 14–15).

In addition to the universities’ investigation, and arguably as an act of considerable institutional overreach, although all institutions that were subjected to the investigation consented to it, according to Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, pp. 3-4, the Central Council of Jews hired a criminal law firm to investigate Homolka’s conduct. Notably, the firm had previously been retained by the Roman Catholic Church to investigate sexual abuse scandals within its ranks. Upon the release of an executive summary of the findings, the council’s

president, Dr. Josef Schuster, stated in December 2022 that “the report [of the law firm, YF] made it clear that Homolka could not continue in his previous roles” (Axelrod 2022).

Homolka didn’t, with the exception of one role, namely his professorship at SJT. None of the findings issued by the university’s investigative commission were deemed sufficient to compromise his status as a tenured civil servant (“beamteter Professor”), which allowed him to retain his position and resume his duties in the fall of 2022.

Surprisingly, there is no public information available, however, as to whether the serious accusation of academic misconduct has been further investigated. This must astonish for numerous reasons. For starters, the University of Potsdam’s investigative commission had recommended explicitly that the allegations be further examined by the appropriate institutional body. Moreover, publicly available evidence suggesting plagiarism is substantial:

On February 16, 2023, one of Germany’s major national newspapers, the *Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung* published an article by the senior journalist Heike Schmoll under the catching headline “Ein Plagiat von mehr als 60 Seiten (which can be translated as: A Plagiarism of More than 60 Pages), printed on page 6 (see Schmoll 2023). The article alleged that more than sixty pages—approximately one quarter—of Homolka’s 1992 PhD dissertation at King’s College London were copied without attribution from an unpublished work by Dorothee Schlenke written in 1986. The source in question is Schlenke’s “Wissenschaftliche Hausarbeit”, which is a qualifying thesis for the German state examination. The thesis was completed in Protestant theology at the University of Munich under the title “Normativität und Geschichte”. Here is one piece of textual evidence that Schmoll (2023) offers: Schlenke (1986, German original, according to Schmoll 2023): „Die Wesensdebatte war so im Kern eine Debatte um die Identität der Beteiligten (138), wobei ein Bewusstsein möglicher Konsonanz, wie die jüdischen Wesensschriften zeigen, durchaus vorhanden war und auch angestrebt wurde.” And, here is what we find in Homolka’s 1992 PhD thesis, according to Schmoll (2023): “Therefore, the core of the essence debate concerned the identity of those concerned (150), whereby a consciousness of possible consonance, as demonstrated in the Jewish writings on subjects, existed indeed and was even aspired to.”

The piece of textual evidence strongly suggests a sentence-level correspondence that exceeds what can be attributed to coincidence or to the use of common academic phrasing. The structure, sequence of ideas, and specific conceptual pairings in the German original

(“Wesensdebatte ... Debatte um die Identität der Beteiligten ... Bewusstsein möglicher Konsonanz ... vorhanden war und auch angestrebt wurde”) are reproduced almost verbatim in Homolka’s English text, with only minimal cosmetic variation (“the core of the essence debate concerned the identity of those concerned ... a consciousness of possible consonance ... existed indeed and was even aspired to”). Even the syntactic placement of subordinate clauses and the dual structure “already present / also aspired to” are retained. Such close similarity—including the replication of an unusual collocation (“awareness/consciousness of possible consonance”)—strongly suggests a near-literal translation of Schlenke’s sentence. Therefore, what Schmoll (2023) argues is certainly not fabricated or baseless.

While Schlenke is later acknowledged in both the German and the English book publications derived from the dissertation, according to Schmoll (2023) no reference to Schlenke appears in the dissertation itself. Schmoll (2023) further reports that, when the *Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung* requested clarification regarding this omission, Homolka—through his lawyer—denied that Schlenke’s work had constituted the main source of his dissertation. Schmoll (2023) also states that the dissertation was removed from the King’s College London online repository on the same day his lawyer issued that statement. In response to a freedom of information request I submitted, King’s College London advised me in a letter dated May 7, 2025: “You requested a digital copy of Dr. Homolka’s thesis, and we confirmed that we hold the information, but are withholding its release due to the author’s request for the digital thesis to be taken down.”

I recognize the complication arising from the fact that the 1992 PhD thesis by Homolka was completed at King’s College London. The University of Potsdam has consistently deferred to King’s in this matter and has indicated publicly that it is awaiting clarification from London as the PhD awarding institution. That was the response I received still in the spring of 2025 when I submitted a freedom of information request to the University of Potsdam. In the fall of 2025, however, the University of Potsdam disclosed to me that King’s had in fact submitted a report to Potsdam and that this report was currently under consideration. The university also disclosed that an additional publication by Homolka had become the subject of a plagiarism inquiry. But even in the absence of a report from King’s, the plagiarism regulations of the University of Potsdam (from February 16, 2022: “Neufassung der Satzung “Selbstkontrolle in der Wissenschaft—Regeln zur Sicherung guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis an der Universität Potsdam”), in § 9(2),

provide the university itself with the authority to take decisive action in cases of serious and substantial allegations of plagiarism.

In light of these norms and disclosures, it is extremely difficult to avoid the impression that the University of Potsdam has, at least thus far, fallen short of the level of due diligence and institutional academic oversight one would expect in handling such allegations. A period of three years is an unusually long time for such an investigation to remain unresolved, especially in light of the substantiveness of the allegations. In the absence of a clear and public resolution by King’s College London or the University of Potsdam, the allegations can only be considered unresolved, and it is difficult to see how the allegations will cease to affect the SJT and its wider institutional academic context.

The “Allgemeine Rabbinerkonferenz” (General Conference of Rabbis hereafter; established in 2005 as part of the German Conference of Rabbis at the Central Council, comprising rabbis of all denominations, unlike the Conference of Orthodox Rabbis) declared in 2023 that it “considers it central and important for the future of Judaism in Germany to continue the training of rabbis and cantors in Potsdam in order to educate qualified personnel for the Jewish community. We call on all parties involved to come together at a round table to make this possible.” (ARK 2024) The declaration was not supported by all rabbis.

This body had excluded Homolka with the required two thirds of the votes (19 in favor, and 8 opposed, see *Jüdische Allgemeine* 2023), on January 25, 2023, a decision that elevated the highly contentious and ambiguous position of Homolka even more.

At the same time, a new organization for liberal Judaism in Germany formed, namely the Jewish liberal-egalitarian Union (“Jüdischer Liberal-Egalitärer Verband”; JLEV), which, unlike UpJ, is part of the Central Council, and counts 10 local Jewish communities and 1 Chavurah as their members (see CCJG 2023b). In effect, there is a schism now in the liberal Jewish community in Germany at the community level. Members of the new union seek distance to Homolka’s continuing influence over liberal Judaism in Germany, especially in the context of UpJ.

Undeterred by the public attention directed at him—and in addition to publicly denying the accusations and initiating legal proceedings against some of his critics, he seeks to participate in the restructuring process that has been underway since 2022. For example, he has made the Jewish community of Berlin the “owner” of the *Träger* of AGK and ZFK (see Gercke

Wollschläger Report 2023, 40 and 65), which he was able to do, because before he did that, he had not only been the head of AGK (rector) and ZFK (Executive Director), but also “owner” of the *Träger* of AGK (CCJH 2023, 40), and also been “in control” of the *Träger* of ZFK (see Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, 65). Both *Träger* are thus out of reach for adoption by the Central Council. Moreover, even influence over AGK and ZFK proves difficult, as the Central Council of Jews and the Jewish community of Berlin have entered a public legal dispute as to the reach of the authority of the council in the affairs of the Jewish community of Berlin (see Thaidigsmann 2024).

These states of affairs explain why the Central Council of Jews established the Nathan Peter Levinson Foundation (NPLF hereafter) that has become the *Träger* of three new seminaries (in addition to AGK and ZFK): “The Nathan Peter Levinson Foundation was established in 2024,” NPLF (2024) reads, “with the aim of bringing academic quality and transparency to the training of the new generation of liberal (Reform) and conservative (Masorti) rabbis and cantors in Germany. The foundation combines a cantorship and two rabbinical seminaries. Studies at the Foundation’s seminaries are integrated with the BA and MA programs at the School of Jewish Theology (University of Potsdam).”

The new seminaries are the Regina Jonas Seminary (training liberal rabbis; RJS hereafter), the Abraham J. Heschel Seminary (training conservative rabbis; AJHS hereafter), and the Louis Lewandowski Seminary (training liberal, conservative, and non-denominational cantors; LLS hereafter).

The University of Potsdam has elected to enter into agreements with the NPFL and the Central Council of Jews (see *Jüdische Allgemeine* 2025), and (as I understand it) public funding for the education of liberal and conservative rabbis and cantors will go exclusively to channels controlled by these three actors to their dependent organizations, i.e., SJT, RJS, AJHS, and LLS. “This new collaboration also marks the conclusion of the Ziegler School’s engagement with the Frankel College in Germany,” Ziegler (2024) reads. The Ziegler School of Rabbinic Studies at the American Jewish University had sponsored the ZFK.

Given all these developments, the future trajectory of the AGK and ZFK remains uncertain amid ongoing restructuring processes. At present, the Central Council of Jews appears to hold institutional leverage, insofar as the developments outlined above can plausibly be framed as a struggle between what some describe as “non-observant orthodoxy” and progressive

Judaism. At the same time, the RJS, AJHS, and LLS are not yet fully functioning seminaries, and the liberal Jewish community continues to experience internal fragmentation. The continued operation of the AGK and ZFK, their affiliation with Germany's largest Jewish community, and the unresolved questions surrounding governance at the SJT all contribute to a landscape in flux.

In this context, it is difficult to assess the long-term prospects of academic Jewish theology in Germany. Public discussion has raised questions about the institutional stability of the SJT, including concerns related to unresolved allegations surrounding Professor Homolka. I take no position on the substance or outcome of these matters; my concern here is limited to their *potential institutional implications*. Should these processes lead to significant changes in leadership or staffing, the SJT could find itself operating with a very limited tenured faculty base—an outcome that would carry consequences for its long-term viability. If Professor Manfred Görtemaker is right in his assessment that any serious investigation into the plagiarism allegations concerning Homolka's dissertation could only conclude that plagiarism occurred (“Ein Plagiat reinsten Wassers”—A plagiarism of the purest kind), and if such a finding were to result in the loss of his professorship (cf. Görtemaker 2023), then the SJT would be left with only one tenured professor.

Against this backdrop, it is worth noting that the AGK and ZFK produced rabbis and cantors before the establishment of the SJT. Likewise, there is no conceptual reason why the RJS, AJHS, or LLS could not continue to train and ordain clergy independently of a university-based Jewish theology department. It is therefore conceivable—though this remains speculative—that rabbinical and cantorial formation in Potsdam might proceed with a stronger reliance on “Jewish Studies” rather than on a distinct academic field of “Jewish Theology”.

(8) Conclusion

I have argued that the Homolka Affair is pivotal for understanding the current situation of academic Jewish theology in Germany. There is significant scholarly merit in analyzing the Homolka Affair as a significant cultural phenomenon, not as a story of an individual's success or failure, but a lens through which the structural and cultural conditions of theology's institutional existence in Germany become visible.

The emergence of the SJT is a more complex phenomenon than it may appear when viewed solely through the lens of institutional history or from a perspective shaped by the expectations of such an account. Throughout my analysis, I have emphasized two axes of tension that converge in the Homolka Affair and thus in the institutional formation of academic Jewish theology at the SJT. The first is the axis of negotiation between different forms of Judaism, which raises corresponding questions about the very possibility of a Jewish theology. The second is the axis of negotiation concerning the identity of post-Shoah Germany and the role that Jewish institutions play in shaping and symbolizing that identity. I have argued that, in the Homolka Affair, these dynamics intersect in a uniquely revealing configuration. There is no need to exaggerate the significance of the Homolka Affair; yet it would be equally mistaken to reduce it to a narrative of individual success or failure. Such a reading appears inadequate to account for the available evidence. Not only key actors involved in the developments examined here appear aware that the Homolka Affair points to deeper structural and cultural processes. “Homolka’s remarkable transformation,” Laura Moser (2023) writes—a transformation from a Christian preacher in 1993 to the most powerful leader in liberal Judaism within a few years—“has to do with the changes Germany itself was undergoing in the decade after the fall of the Berlin Wall.” Certainly, elements of personal acrimony are present, but that layer of the Homolka Affair is likely the least instructive for understanding the broader German context of academic Jewish theology.

Consideration of policy recommendations, the rediscovery of pre-Shoah visions of a Jewish theological faculty, and the “reforestation” ideology within Germany’s political culture—while certainly important—are insufficient to account for the developments surrounding the SJT. Based on the available evidence, it is difficult to accept that the recent emergence of academic Jewish theology in Germany can be explained merely as a bureaucratic implementation of the *Wissenschaftsrat*’s 2010 recommendations, as a revival of the ideals of the *Wissenschaft des Judentums* (Science of Judaism), or as the outcome of a “reforestation” ideology. Nor can it be understood solely as a pragmatic response to rapid changes within the Jewish community, the broader transformation of academic theology at public universities, or political decisions concerning the relationship between state and religious communities. The same holds for other contributing factors, some of which discussed earlier—among them the Central Council’s claims

to sole representation of the Jewish community in Germany, challenges to “non-observant orthodoxy,” ambitions for religious leadership, the University of Potsdam’s efforts to consolidate its pioneering role in Jewish studies, the expansion of its already substantial Jewish Studies program, the federal state of Brandenburg’s aspiration to raise its national profile (closely tied to the university’s growing reputation), and liberal Judaism’s pursuit of institutional recognition and the training of clergy.

Rather than being reducible to any single factor or even to their cumulative effect, my analysis suggests that the Homolka Affair crystallizes in unique ways the mutually reinforcing forces that arise from the tensions among these factors in conjunction with Homolka’s extraordinarily ambiguous and contentious position. In this sense, the Homolka Affair functions as a site where the epistemic, institutional, and political forces shaping Jewish theology in Germany intersect and are continually renegotiated. Homolka’s position is not merely symptomatic but constitutive: it operates as a boundary phenomenon through which the meaning of “Jewish theology” itself—its legitimacy, institutional form, and epistemic orientation—is being redefined. The figure of Homolka is thus pivotal not primarily with regard to his actions as individual, intentional or otherwise, but in the technical sense articulated by Marc D. Baer (2020), who interprets Hugo Marcus—gay, Jewish by birth, a convert to Islam, and a citizen of the Weimar Republic—as a revealing cultural formation through which to discern deeper currents of political culture, in Jasanoff’s (2005) sense of the term. In a nutshell, what my discussion in this paper therefore suggests is that Homolka’s *Grenzgänger* position—his existence at the intersection of religious and cultural frontiers—is central to understanding the distinctive dynamics that have shaped academic Jewish theology in Germany today.

On one axis, his background in Christianity and his subsequent conversion to Judaism in 1986—followed by the fact that he delivered a Christian sermon in 1993 and, as Moser (2023) alleges, has exhibited a persistent inability to recite even the most basic Jewish prayers—produce an epistemic hybridity that helped normalize the very notion of “Jewish theology” within an intellectual horizon still shaped by Christian categories of systematic and doctrinal thought. This disposition helps to explain his readiness to model Jewish theology on the Christian faculty system, without offering a sustained account of the tensions such a move creates within a contemporary Judaism that has been emancipated from centuries of Christian oppression. It is, I

argue, surely simplistic to align the nineteenth-century usage of the term “Jewish theology” and calls for a Jewish theological faculty with developments in the twenty-first century along a linear progressive history, and to claim historical continuity in terms of utopian vision and final realization culminating in SJT (see Homolka 2015). Such a move misconstrues the value judgments and negotiations around legitimacy, community, and authority that define every system of public knowledge, as stressed by Feyerabend (1975), systematically conceptualized by Kitcher (2011), and demonstrated in this paper.

On the other axis, his position as a *native German* convert to Judaism shapes a publicly articulated relationship to the Shoah that differs from that often expressed by leaders in the Central Council of Jews, many of whom are bound to its memory through direct family loss and for whom theological restraint and communal protection remain moral imperatives. In public discourse and statements associated with Homolka’s vision for Jewish theology, the Shoah is frequently framed more in terms of reconciliation and renewal than as inherited trauma. After all, one must also account for the fact that the Central Council of Jews in Germany, despite its institutional authority and political power, did not establish an academic institution for the training of rabbis and cantors, continuing instead to rely on clergy educated abroad.

In this dual sense, Homolka’s ambiguous and contentious position embodies the intersection of the two axes that structure my discussion in this paper—the religious-epistemic and the political-historical—and thus constitutes a key condition under which Jewish theological discourse in Germany could be reimagined and institutionalized in the form of the SJT. Conceptually, Homolka’s *Grenzgänger* position performs what Sheila Jasanoff (2005) terms *coproduction*: the simultaneous making of social and epistemic orders. The redefinition of Jewish theology in Germany cannot be separated from the negotiations over political culture and collective identity that accompany it. In this respect, Homolka’s role also resonates with Feyerabend’s pluralism, which calls attention to the generative potential of epistemic conflict and the productive friction between competing traditions of thought. The Homolka Affair thus becomes not merely a case of personal controversy, but a most revealing episode in the ongoing coproduction of a system of public knowledge, religious tradition, and political culture in post-Shoah Germany, with considerable implications for academic Jewish theology.

References

- ARK. 2024. "Rabbiner- und Kantorenausbildung in Potsdam." June 24, 2024, <https://a-r-k.de/meldung/137/> (last accessed, June 11, 2025).
- Axelrod, Toby. 2022. "Prominent German rabbi exits leadership roles as report confirms allegations against him." *Jewish Telegraphy Agency*, December 7, 2022. <https://www.jta.org/2022/12/07/global/prominent-german-rabbi-resigns-from-leadership-roles-as-report-confirms-allegations-against-him> (last accessed June 1, 2025).
- _____. 2007. "A lone groan for female rabbi in Berlin." *Jewish Telegraphy Agency*, March 31, 2007. <https://www.jta.org/2007/05/31/lifestyle/a-lone-groan-for-female-rabbi-in-berlin> (last accessed June 1, 2025).
- Baer, Marc D. 2020. *The Life and Times of Hugo Marcus*. Columbia University Press.
- Berger, Peter. 2014. *The Many Altars of Modernity: Toward a Paradigm for Religion in a Pluralist Age*. De Gruyter.
- Brink, Gijsbert van den. 2020. "The future of theology at public universities." *In die Skriflig* 50(2), a2583. <https://doi.org/10.4102/ids.v54i2.2583>.
- British Academy. 2019. *Theology and Religious Studies Provision in UK Higher Education*. <https://www.thebritishacademy.ac.uk/publications/theology-religious-studies-provision-uk-higher-education/> (last accessed May 30, 2025).
- Brooke, John H. 1991. *Science and Religion: Some Historical Perspectives*. Cambridge University Press.
- Brumlik, Micha. 1995. "The Development of Jewish Religious Life in Postwar Germany." In: *Speaking Out: Jewish Voices from United Germany*, ed. by. Susan Stern, pp. 211-218. edition q, inc.
- CCJG. 2023b. "Gründung JLEV." April 20, 2023. <https://www.zentralratderjuden.de/presseerklaerungen/gruendung-jlev/> (last accessed June 10, 2025).
- De Lange, Nicholas R. M. 2000. *An Introduction to Judaism*. Cambridge University Press.
- Diamond, James A. 2018. *Jewish Theology Unbound*. Oxford University Press.
- Efron, Noah J. 2007. *Judaism and Science: A historical Introduction*. Greenwood Press.
- Elliot, Kevin C. 2022. *Values in Science*. Cambridge University Press.
- Fackenheim, Emil L. 1987. *What is Judaism? An Interpretation for the Present Age*. Summit Books.
- Feyerabend, Paul. *Science in a Free Society*. Verso Books.
- _____. 1975. *Against Method*. Verso Books.
- Fisch, Menachem. 2017. "Proving by Miracle: The Myth History of Talmudic Judaism's Coming of Age." *Toronto Journal of Theology* 33 (S1): 103-127.
- Geiger, Abraham. 1836. "Die Gründung einer jüdisch-theologischen Facultät, ein dringendes Bedürfniß unserer Zeit." *Wissenschaftliche Zeitschrift für Jüdische Theologie* 2: 1-21.

Gercke Wollschläger Report. 2023. *Untersuchungsbericht zu etwaigem Fehlverhalten von Herrn Rabbiner Prof. Dr. Dr. Walter Homolka und dessen Lebensgefährten gegenüber Studierenden und sonstigen Angehörigen verschiedener jüdischer Einrichtungen—einschließlich Ursachenanalyse und Handlungsempfehlungen—der Kanzlei Gercke Wollschläger*. Köln, den 13.09.2023.

Görtemaker, Manfred. 2023. Interview with Deutschlandfunk: “Als wäre nichts gewesen? Was folgt aus dem Gutachten zur Causa Walter Homolka? Dippel, Carsten | 30. Oktober 2023, 09:44 Uhr. <https://www.deutschlandfunk.de/als-waere-nichts-gewesen-was-folgt-aus-dem-gutachten-zur-causa-walter-homolka-dlf-17d8dad6-100.html>

Goldmann, Ayala. 2023. “»Die unsinnige Trennung aufgeben«.” *Jüdische Allgemeine* 08.01.2023. (last accessed June 9, 2025).

Gross, Leonard. 1999. *The Last Jews in Berlin*. Carroll & Graf Publishers, Inc.

Habermas, Jürgen. 2023. *Also a History of Philosophy. Volume I. The Project of a Genealogy of Postmetaphysical Thinking*. Translated by Ciaran Cronin. Polity Press.

Hammerstein, Notker. 2014. “Die Frankfurter Universität – eine besondere Hochschule.” In: *Forschung Frankfurt* No. 1/2014: 5-7.

Harrison, Peter. 2015. *The Territories of Science and Religion*. Chicago University Press.

Heckel, Martin. 1986. *Die theologischen Fakultäten im weltlichen Verfassungsstaat*. Mohr Siebeck.

Heckel, Martin. 1987. *Organisationsstrukturen der Theologie in der Universität*. Duncker & Humblot.

Homolka, Walter. 2015. “When a Utopia Became Reality: Jewish Studies and Jewish Theology Well Established in Germany.” *Toronto Journal of Theology* 31: 197-202.

Homolka, Walter, and Hans-Gert Pöttering, eds. 2013. *Theologie(n) an der Universität: Akademische Herausforderung im säkularen Umfeld*. Berlin/Boston: De Gruyter.

Hazon, Yoram. 2012. *The Philosophy of Hebrew Scripture*. Cambridge University Press.

Howard, Thomas A. 2006. *Protestant Theology and the Making of the Modern German University*. Oxford University Press.

Jasanoff, Sheila. 2005. *Designs on Nature: Science and Democracy in Europe and the United States*. Princeton University Press.

Jüdische Allgemeine. 2025. “»Herausragender Moment für das jüdische Leben in Deutschland«,” 17.09.2025. <https://www.juedische-allgemeine.de/politik/herausragender-moment-fuer-das-juedische-leben-in-deutschland/> (last accessed June 1, 2025)

_____. 2023. “»Ein wichtiger Schritt«,” 02.02.2023. <https://www.juedische-allgemeine.de/unsere-woche/ein-wichtiger-schritt-3/?q=Homolka> (last accessed June 8, 2025).

_____. 2022. “Kolleg-Gründer Walter Homolka ist wieder als Professor im Dienst,” 26.10.2022. <https://www.juedische-allgemeine.de/unsere-woche/nach-vorwuerfen-kolleg-gruender-walter-homolka-ist-wieder-als-professor-im-dienst/> (last accessed June 1, 2025).

_____. 2020. “Rabbiner Walter Homolka im Amt bestätigt,” 11.09.2020. <https://www.juedische-allgemeine.de/religion/rabbiner-walter-homolka-im-amt-bestaetigt/> (last accessed June 1, 2025).

_____. 2011. “Das Potsdamer Rabbinerseminar streckt seine Fühler nach Bayern aus,” 14.11.2011. <https://www.juedische-allgemeine.de/religion/rabbiner-walter-homolka-im-amt-bestaetigt/> (last accessed May 30, 2025)

Kaplan, Lawrence. 1973. “The Religious Philosophy of Rabbi Joseph Soloveitchik.” *Tradition: A Journal of Orthodox Jewish Thought* 14: 43-64.

Kaufmann, Uri R. “On the Way to Pluralism? Jewish Communities in Germany Today.” In: *Speaking Out: Jewish Voices from United Germany*, ed. by. Susan Stern, pp. 28-38. edition q, inc.

Kitcher, Philip. 2011. *Science in a Democratic Society*. Prometheus Books.

Krampitz, Klaus. 2023. “Walter Homolka: Die Geschichte hinter den Vorwürfen.” <https://www.nd-aktuell.de/artikel/1171302.walter-homolka-walter-homolka-die-geschichte-hinter-den-vorwuerfen.html> (last accessed June 1, 2025).

Kuhn, Thomas S. 1962. *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. The University of Chicago Press.

Lebrecht, Norman. 2020. *Genius & Anxiety: How Jews changed the world, 1847-1947*. Scribner.

Levinson, Nathan Peter. 1996. *Ein Ort ist, mit wem Du bist: Lebensstationen eines Rabbiners*. Schriften der Neuen Synagoge Berlin. Centrum Judaicum. Edition Hentrich.

Markschies, Christoph. 2020. “Theologische Fakultäten an staatlichen Universitäten in Deutschland heute.” In *Reformation der Kirche – Reform der Bildung: Die Universität Marburg und der reformatorische Bildungsauftrag*, edited by Wolf-Friedrich Schäufele, pp. 255–291. Münster: Acta Marburgensis 16.

Moser, Laura. 2023. “In Bad Faith.” <https://airmail.news/issues/2023-5-6/in-bad-faith>. Last retrieved November 18, 2025.

Nachama, Andreas. 2024. “Glauben und Zweifel: Die wollen uns torpedieren”: An interview with Andreas Nachama by Evelyn Finger, published in *DIE ZEIT* on June 20, 2024. <https://www.zeit.de/2024/27/andreas-nachama-walter-homolka-machtmissbrauch-universitaet> (last accessed May 30, 2025).

NPLF. 2024. “About Us.” <https://www.levinson-stiftung.de/en/home-page/aboutus/> (last accessed, June 10, 2025).

Putnam, Hilary. 2002. *The Collapse of the Fact/Value Dichotomy and Other Essays*. Harvard University Press.

Posener, Alan. 2022b. “Die brisanten Hintergründe des Systems Homolka,” *Welt*, May 30, 2025. <https://www.welt.de/kultur/plus239018441/Walter-Homolka-So-wurde-sein-System-ermoeeglicht.html> (last accessed June 2, 2025).

2022. “Die Methode Homolka.” *Welt*, May 6, 2022. <https://www.welt.de/kultur/plus238562571/Missbrauchsskandal-am-Potsdamer-Geiger-Kolleg-Die-Methode-Homolka.html> (last accessed June 2, 2025).

Ruphy, Stephanie. 2016. *Scientific Pluralism Reconsidered: A New Approach to the (Dis-)Unity of Science*. Pittsburgh University Press.

Schmoll, Heike. 2023. "Ein Plagiat von mehr als 60 Seiten." FAZ, February 17, 2023. <https://www.faz.net/aktuell/politik/inland/abraham-geiger-kolleg-homolkas-dissertation-mit-60-seiten-plagiat-18681146.html> (last accessed May 30, 2025).

Schorsch, Jonathan. 2023. "Back to the Big German Rabbinical Scandal." <https://jonathanschorsch.wordpress.com/2023/05/15/1215/> (last accessed June 11, 2025)

Thaidigsmann, Michael. 2024. "Zentralrat der Juden entzieht der Jüdischen Gemeinde zu Berlin das Stimmrecht." *Jüdische Allgemeine*, 27.02.2024. <https://www.juedische-allgemeine.de/kultur/zentralrat-der-juden-entzieht-der-juedischen-gemeinde-zu-berlin-das-stimmrecht/> (last accessed June 3, 2025).

Tzuberi, Hannah. 2020. "'Reforestation' Jews: The German State and the Construction of 'New German Judaism.'" *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 27: 199-224.

Universität Potsdam. 2022. *Bericht der Untersuchungskommission zur Aufarbeitung der Vorgänge im Bereich der Jüdischen Theologie (School of Jewish Theology (SoJT)) der Universität Potsdam*. https://www.uni-potsdam.de/fileadmin/projects/up/images/medienmitteilungen/PM_2022/2022_119_Bericht_SoJT.pdf (last accessed May 30, 2025).

Welt. 2022. "Landesregierung droht Woelki mit Verletzungsverfahren beim Vatikan." <https://www.welt.de/regionales/nrw/article241181599/Priesterausbildung-Landesregierung-droht-Woelki-mit-Vertragsverletzungsverfahren-beim-Vatikan.html> (last accessed June 3, 2025).

Wiese, Christian. 1999. "Wissenschaft des Judentums und protestantische Theologie im wilhelminischen Deutschland: Ein Schrei ins Leere?" Mohr Siebeck.

Wissenschaftsrat (Council of Science and Humanities). 2010. *Recommendations on the Advancement of Theologies and Sciences Concerned with Religions at German Universities (Drs. 9678-10_engl)*. January 2010.

Wolffsohn, Michael. 1995. "Plea for an Inwardly Directed German Nationalism." In: *Speaking Out: Jewish Voices from United Germany*, ed. by. Susan Stern, pp. 126-137. edition q, inc.

Ziegler. 2024. "American Jewish University and Central Conference of Jews in Germany Lead Historic Initiative to Revitalize Jewish Life in Europe." September 16, 2024. <https://www.aju.edu/newsroom/american-jewish-university-and-central-conference-jews-germany-lead-historic-initiative> (last accessed June 9, 2025).